

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF RESEARCHES THAT STUDIED HISTORICAL PEOPLE, PARTICULARLY BABUR IN LITERATURE.

Khayrullayeva Kamola Ravshanovna

Independent Researcher of Bukhara State University

E -mail: khayrullayevakamola95@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article deals with the researches based on the literary books about the life and deeds of historical personalities. Wide range of details are given about the researchers who investigated the usage of historical people in literary works as a main character.

Key words: Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Amir Temur, historical person, novel, play, Samarkand, historians, Central Asia, Southern Asia, India.

Introduction

Writing works dedicated to the life path of historical figures is a unique trend in world literature. In this sense, the study of such works has been relevant in literary studies in all periods. In this article, information is presented in the case of several researchers who have conducted research on the issue of the embodiment of historical figures in fiction.

Main part

D. Q. Naimova also analyzed and interpreted the works written abroad about our great ancestor Amir Temur. In this regard, the novel, short story, plays written dedicated to the history of Timurid and Timurid period are identified, and it is noted that they gained great fame on the European stage.

In Uzbek literary studies, researches related to the interpretation of historical figures, especially the image of Babur, have also been carried out. For example, U. Sultanova in the article "Description of heroic characters in Pirimkul Kadyrov's novel "Starry Nights"" immortal novel about the king and poet is not only dedicated to the life of Babur, but also a rare work that can fully show the history and past of ordinary people. admits that As a proof of his opinion, he gives an example of the dangerous life of Tahir and his lover Rabia, who were representatives of the common people in the play, but who were among Zahiriddin's loyal servants due to their loyalty. In addition, the situation of ordinary citizens who suffered from hunger during the siege of Samarkand or the events that took place while they were wandering in the mountains and rocks also attract attention. Continuing his thoughts, the researcher expresses his views on the kingdom in India founded by Babur. Although Babur was unable

to reunify his grandfather's Sahibqiran state, he managed to establish a peaceful and peaceful kingdom in India.

G. Zoirova conducted her research on the scientific heritage left by foreign historians and writers who showed interest in Babur. It mentions the names of Indian writer Jawaharlal Nehru, Sanam Ali Khan, English historian and writers Edward Holden, William Erskine, Stephen Meredith Edwards, who wrote works on the history of Babur and the great empire founded by Babur. Their incomparable contributions to the development of cultural changes, horticulture, and architecture in India by Babur and his later generations are discussed. The researcher focuses on the place of Babur in the history of India, Babur is the founder of Indian civilization in the whole world, he emphasizes that the Babur dynasty made a great contribution to the development of the country, even though it caused sharp debates in India itself.

Another Pakistani scholar, Zahid Anwar, who worked on the issue of Babur's significant contribution to the development of Central Asia and South Asia, writes that Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur founded a new country with the help of a sword, but he made many artists and scientists in this country. he was able to create a wonderful nature that he was able to attract. He not only developed military technologies, but also made changes to agricultural production mechanisms. The Mongol Empire also had a great influence on horticulture in India. Changes have also taken place in the field of economy, in particular, trade between the two countries has flourished.

One of the researchers who comparatively studied the works about Babur is Ikhtiyor Kamolov. His dissertation on the topic "Biographical approach to the interpretation of the image of Babur in historical and artistic sources" attracts special attention in this regard. Among them are "Babur - Tiger" by the famous American writer Harold Lamb, "The Prince of Andijan" by F. Wuertle, "Tarihi Rashidi" by Mirzo Muhammad Haidar, "Humoyunnoma" by Gulbadanbegim, "Starry Nights" by P. Kadirov, "Beach of Happiness" by H. Sultanov. His works were selected as the object of research. In the dissertation, the scientific, historical and artistic sources covering Babur's life and work are classified chronologically, the historical works of historians such as Gulbadanbegim, Muhammad Haydar Mirzo, Hafiz Kohakiy, Khondamir, Hasanbek Rumlu, Khudoyorkhonzoda and the researches made in the new era of Uzbek Babur studies are analyzed based on the biographical approach. and in the works of historians such as J. Leyden, W. Erskine, A. Beveridge, and Western writers such as H. Lamb, F. Wuertle, Babur is a poet, prose writer, great general, statesman,

who puts the interests of the people above his own interests. his artistic image as the leader of the nation, his personality were studied in a comparative aspect based on the principles of the biographical method. In this regard, the following opinions of the scientist are important: "In the West, especially in English-speaking oriental studies, Babur studies was formed earlier. This is related to the occupation of India by England. The subject of Babur in Russian literary studies was formed in the 18th century. Scientific research began at the beginning of the 19th century. Babur studies in the West initially focused on the analysis and translation of "Baburnoma" and the research of Babur's biography.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that historical figures have been used by writers as protagonists in fiction for many years. This gives the students the opportunity to get acquainted with history and to use the life experiences of historical figures in their own life paths at the same time. It is also known from the above information that many researchers have conducted their research on the issue of using historical figures as images. It is gratifying to note that the image of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, who left a name in history with his creativity and fair management along with our great ancestors Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Mirza Ulug'bek, is widely covered not only in Uzbek literature, but also in English literature.

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